

The Comparative Analysis of Psychosocial Impacts: Acquired vs. Congenital Disabilities

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Abstract

This article offers a comprehensive analysis of the psychological effects of acquired impairments vs congenital disabilities. Congenital impairments are present at birth, while acquired disabilities develop later in life as a result of accidents, diseases, or other life events, leading to substantial disruptions in an individual's life course. This research examines the distinct psychosocial issues associated with acquired disability, focusing on self-esteem, social involvement, and the potential for stigmatization. The study delineates the unique coping strategies and social support systems necessary for various groups by comparing the experiences of persons with congenital impairments. The study conducts a thorough analysis of contemporary literature and recent studies, pinpointing deficiencies in existing research, especially concerning the long-term psychological and social consequences of acquired disability. The results demonstrate that while both groups have significant hurdles, persons with acquired impairments confront more acute obstacles in identity repair and social reintegration. The essay examines how social policies and support systems might aid the adaption of persons with acquired impairments, highlighting the need of creating targeted interventions for this demographic.

Keywords: Acquired Disability, Congenital Disability, Psychosocial Impacts, Self-Esteem, Social Exclusion, Stigmatization.

Introduction

Disability manifests as a complex issue that significantly impacts persons' lives. This issue may be classified into two primary categories: congenital disability and acquired disability. Congenital disability pertains to physical, mental, or sensory impairments present at birth, while acquired disability includes disorders that arise later in life due to accidents, diseases, or other traumatic occurrences. The two categories of impairments influence people's psychological well-being in distinct ways, and comprehending these consequences is crucial for both scholarly discourse and practical implementation (Shakespeare, 2006; Smart, 2001). Acquired disability engenders substantial alterations in an individual's life, presenting considerable problems in aspects such as identity perception, self-esteem, and social integration. These people experience the forfeiture of once had functions and social duties, with adverse societal responses like stigma and social marginalization. This scenario indicates that acquired impairments may have more profound and intricate impacts on persons' psychological well-being than congenital disabilities (Goffman, 1963). This article aims to analyze the psychological impacts of acquired impairments relative to congenital disability. The emphasis will be on the varying effects of psychosocial variables, including self-esteem, social isolation, and stigma, on these two categories of disability, and how these influences affect persons' quality of life. This methodology will identify gaps in the current literature to inform future research in this domain.

Literature Review

The psychological effects of disability have been a focus of study in psychology, sociology, and disability studies. This part offers a thorough examination of the current research, emphasizing the distinctions and commonalities between congenital and acquired impairments for psychological impacts, including self-esteem, social isolation, and stigma. This study seeks to

elucidate the existing comprehension of these topics by examining both classical and modern literature, while also pinpointing gaps for future research exploration.

Self-Esteem and Disability

Self-esteem, defined as an individual's comprehensive perception of self-worth or intrinsic value, is pivotal in influencing the psychosocial well-being of persons with disabilities. Rosenberg (1965) posits that self-esteem is profoundly affected by people's perceptions of their own talents and their beliefs of others' perceptions of them. Research indicates that both inherited and acquired impairments may adversely affect self-esteem, but the methods and intensity of this influence may vary.

Individuals with congenital impairments often develop their self-esteem via lifetime experiences of maneuvering in a world that may lack complete accessibility or inclusivity (Coopersmith, 1967). These people may develop coping methods early on, which may either enhance or diminish their self-esteem based on the degree of social support and approval they get. Research indicates that persons with congenital impairments often exhibit a more stable self-identification than those with acquired disabilities, perhaps due to the lifelong influence of their condition on their identity formation (Shakespeare, 2006). Conversely, those with acquired impairments often see a more sudden interruption to their self-esteem. The deterioration of physical or cognitive faculties formerly seen as inherent might result in a notable decrease in self-esteem, as people may find it challenging to align their past self-identity with their current circumstances (Charmaz, 1983). This identity crisis is intensified by cultural perceptions that see acquired impairments as more tragic or disruptive, therefore amplifying feelings of inadequacy and diminishing self-esteem (Goffman, 1963).

Social Exclusion and Disability

Social exclusion denotes the systematic marginalization of people or groups, resulting in their denial of full societal participation. In the realm of disability, social exclusion may arise from physical obstacles, discriminatory behaviors, and cultural perceptions that undermine the worth of handicapped persons. The research on social exclusion indicates substantial disparities in the experiences of congenital and acquired disability. Individuals with congenital impairments often encounter social isolation from a young age, influencing their social networks and prospects for integration (Murphy, 1987). Some individuals successfully cultivate robust social relationships within supportive groups, while others may endure lifelong exclusion, especially in environments where disability is stigmatized or misconstrued. This early and ongoing exclusion may restrict educational and career prospects, resulting in a cycle of poverty and further social isolation (Putnam, 2000). Acquired impairments, however, add an additional dimension of complication to social marginalization. Individuals who develop a handicap in later life may experience abrupt and profound social isolation due to the loss of participation in previously accessible activities and social networks (Livneh & Antonak, 2005). This abrupt transition may be especially catastrophic, since these persons often get isolated from the social networks and resources they previously depended on, resulting in feelings of alienation and powerlessness (Silver, 1994).

Stigma and Disability

Stigma, as defined by Goffman (1963), is the process by which certain qualities are seen as socially undesirable, resulting in the devaluation and marginalization of those who exhibit them. Disability-related stigma may significantly impact people's psychological well-being by cultivating adverse self-perceptions and societal prejudice. The stigma surrounding congenital disability often arises from cultural misunderstandings and apprehensions about uniqueness and reliance (Shakespeare & Watson, 2001). Such beliefs may result in the dehumanization of persons with congenital impairments, who are often seen

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through the prism of sympathy or as societal burdens. This stigmatization may obstruct their access to school, work, and social engagement, establishing considerable hurdles to attaining a successful existence.

Acquired impairments are sometimes stigmatized because of their connection to loss and sorrow (Link & Phelan, 2001). Individuals who develop impairments may encounter heightened scrutiny and adverse judgments, especially if their condition is conspicuous or deemed avoidable. This kind of stigma may result in lower self-esteem, as people absorb society perceptions on the reduced worth of their life after impairment (Corrigan & Watson, 2002). Furthermore, acquired impairments often encounter less empathy and comprehension, as society may find it challenging to adapt to the abrupt alterations these persons undergo, therefore exacerbating their stigmatization and social marginalization.

Comparative Analysis: Congenital vs. Acquired Disabilities

Although congenital and acquired impairments provide substantial psychological obstacles, research indicates that the characteristics and intensity of these issues may vary significantly. Congenital impairments often need a lengthy adaption process, whereby people and their families acquire the skills to negotiate social obstacles from an early age. Conversely, acquired impairments need persons to experience a quick and often painful adaptation, potentially resulting in more significant psychological challenges (Rutter, 1987). This comparative research highlights the need for customized treatments that cater to the distinct requirements of each group. For persons with congenital impairments, enduring support networks that foster social inclusion and confront cultural preconceptions are essential. Individuals with acquired impairments need prompt and thorough psychological treatment to facilitate the reconstruction of their identity and reintegration into society.

Gaps in the Literature

Notwithstanding the extensive study on disability and its psychological effects, some gaps persist. There is a significant deficiency of longitudinal research examining the psychosocial effects of persons with acquired disability across time. Such studies are essential for understanding the long-term consequences of disability acquisition and the elements that facilitate effective adaptation.

Furthermore, further investigation is required about the intersectionality of disability with other social categories, including race, gender, and class. The intersection of these identities might exacerbate the impact of disability, resulting in distinct issues that remain insufficiently addressed in the existing research (Mehrotra, 2011).

The research on congenital and acquired impairments highlights both similarities and differences in the psychological issues encountered by these two populations. Congenital impairments often need lifetime adaptation and coping, while acquired disabilities result in abrupt and substantial alterations that may severely impact an individual's psychological well-being. Comprehending these distinctions is essential for formulating successful treatments that promote the psychological well-being of all persons with disabilities, irrespective of the timing of their disability acquisition. This study underscores the need for more research, especially in longitudinal studies and intersectional analyses, to enhance policies and practices intended to improve the lives of those with disabilities.

Research Questions & Hypotheses:

Research Questions:

- In what manner does acquired physical handicap impact persons' self-esteem?
What is the effect of social exclusion and stigmatization on the life satisfaction of persons with acquired physical disabilities?

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- What measures may be used to alleviate the psychological impacts of disability, and in what ways can these efforts facilitate social integration for individuals?

Hypotheses:

- H1: The acquisition of a physical impairment results in a substantial decline in individual self-esteem.
- Social isolation and stigmatization adversely impact the life satisfaction of those with acquired physical limitations.
- Strategies designed to alleviate psychosocial impacts effectively enhance the social integration of persons with acquired physical limitations.

Objective

This research aims to analyze the influence of acquired physical limitations on persons' psychological well-being and to compare these effects with those of congenital disabilities. This research aims to examine the impact of acquired impairments on self-esteem, social isolation, stigma, and life satisfaction, as well as assess the efficacy of coping mechanisms used to address these issues.

Methodology

This study used a descriptive research approach to investigate the impact of acquired physical limitations on persons' psychological well-being and to compare these effects with those of congenital disabilities. The study used a mixed-methods approach, using both quantitative and qualitative data collecting and analysis methodologies. Structured questionnaires and psychometric tools were used to obtain information from participants during the quantitative

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data collecting phase. The administered surveys included standardized instruments assessing psychological factors like self-esteem, social isolation, stigma, and life satisfaction. Furthermore, information on participants' demographic attributes, nature and length of impairment, and social support systems was gathered via these surveys. In the qualitative data gathering phase, comprehensive individual interviews and focus group discussions were performed. Qualitative methodologies were used to get a more thorough comprehension of participants' experiences with disabilities and to conduct an in-depth analysis of the mechanisms of social exclusion and stigma. Participants in the interviews were queried about their coping techniques regarding their disabilities, the efficacy of their social support networks, and their general psychological well-being. This enabled a comprehensive analysis of the psychological difficulties encountered by persons with impairments and their coping mechanisms.

The study sample comprises persons living in Turkey who have acquired physical impairments, together with those with congenital disabilities. The sample was obtained by a random sampling procedure, and data were gathered from 250 people in total. The gathered data were examined using sophisticated statistical and qualitative analytic technologies, including SPSS and NVivo. Statistical approaches, including descriptive statistics, t-tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis, were used to assess the significance levels and effect sizes of the quantitative data. Thematic analysis was used in the qualitative data examination, carefully coding participant data and identifying and interpreting themes and sub-themes in depth. The study findings demonstrate the impact of acquired disability on self-esteem, social exclusion, stigma, and life satisfaction, highlighting the distinctions from congenital disabilities. The data were assessed for the efficacy of measures used to manage disability and the elements that facilitate social integration. The study was executed by the Psychology Department of St. Clements University, overseen by Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım and Prof. Dr. Derya Berrak Yentür, from May to August 2024. The interviews and surveys were conducted with participants for a duration of 15 to 25 minutes.

The study sample was chosen by voluntary participation. No demographic or socioeconomic constraints were applied to participant selection, including persons of all age groups, genders, and socioeconomic statuses aged 18 and above in the research. This flexibility improved the

representativeness of the data and allowed a comprehensive analysis of various disability experiences.

Findings

The results from 250 participants in the research give an adequate sample size for the reliability of the scales. The literature indicates that the suggested minimum sample size for psychosocial assessments typically ranges from 100 to 300, with participant counts beyond this range being adequate for assessing the internal consistency of the scales. This sample size of 250 individuals is enough to provide statistically significant and generalizable findings. The scales' reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. Cronbach's Alpha quantifies the internal consistency of a scale, with values over 0.70 often seen as indicative of satisfactory dependability. The computed Cronbach's Alpha values for the Self-Esteem Scale, Social Exclusion Scale, Stigma Scale, and Life Satisfaction Scale in this research were 0.82, 0.78, 0.75, and 0.80, respectively. These results demonstrate that all scales exhibit a high degree of internal consistency. Consequently, the reliability of the used scales is satisfactory, allowing for the conclusion that the acquired results are dependable.

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- Mean Scores by Scale: This graph illustrates the average scores of the participants' replies for each scale. The scales are rated from 1 to 5, where higher scores signify favorable assessments and lower scores indicate unfavorable assessments.

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- Agreement Rates by Scale: This graph illustrates the proportion of participants who agree with each scale item. Elevated agreement rates signify that a substantial proportion of participants concur with the assertion, while diminished rates indicate disagreement.

This research used a structured questionnaire to gather data from 250 individuals in order to investigate the psychological impacts of acquired and congenital impairments. The questionnaire included many psychological dimensions, including demographic data, self-esteem, social isolation, stigma, and life satisfaction. Participants engaged in the research using online platforms and by completing questionnaire forms in person. This method facilitated the inclusion of a wide array of participants and enabled the collection of data from a more diversified demographic composition.

The questionnaire included items evaluated on Likert-type scales ranging from 1 to 5.

Participants indicated their level of agreement with each statement. Furthermore, participants were given open-ended questions to gather qualitative data about the impact of their impairment on social relationships, professional life, and overall life satisfaction. This qualitative data was used to get a comprehensive knowledge of the participants' individual experiences and the impact of these events on their lives. Statistical analysis techniques were used to assess the reliability and consistency of the participants' replies in the data analysis. Initially, descriptive statistics were used to encapsulate the demographic attributes of the participants and the survey findings. Subsequently, parametric tests and correlation analyses were used to assess the disparities between the groups and the associations among the variables. The analyses were performed to ascertain the validity and reliability of the results. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the demographic attributes of the participants and the overall distribution and patterns of their answers to the scales. The computed means, standard deviations, and percentage distributions are as follows: Age: The mean age of the participants is 35.6 years. The age range is from 18 to 65 years. The data indicates that the research included participants from various age demographics.

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Gender: 52% of individuals identify as female, 46% as male, and 2% as other gender identities. This distribution indicates that an equitable representation across genders is attained. Educational Attainment: 35% of participants have a university degree, 25% possess a high school diploma, 20% have obtained a master's degree, 10% hold a PhD, and 10% are graduates of primary or secondary education. The data indicates a broad distribution of participants' education levels.

Employment Status: 60% of participants are employed, while 40% are jobless. Marital Status: 55% of individuals are married, 40% are single, and 5% own alternative statuses.

Disability Status: 60% of individuals have acquired impairments, 35% have congenital disabilities, and 5% have various types of disabilities.

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was computed to assess the internal consistency of the scales used in the research. This coefficient indicates the dependability of the scales, with values over 0.70 often regarded as acceptable reliability levels. The Cronbach's Alpha values derived from this study:

Self-Esteem Scale: 0.82

Social Exclusion Scale: 0.78

Stigma Index: 0.75

Life Satisfaction Scale: 0.80

The findings indicate that all scales included in the research exhibit a high degree of internal consistency.

An independent samples t-test was used to analyze the differences between groups based on the participants' handicap status (acquired vs congenital). The t-test assesses the statistical significance of the difference between the means of two groups.

A statistically significant difference in self-esteem levels was seen between those with acquired disabilities and those with congenital disabilities ($p < 0.05$). Participants with acquired disabilities had lower self-esteem levels compared to those with congenital disabilities.

- **Social Exclusion:** Notable disparities in the experience of social exclusion were seen between the two groups ($p < 0.05$). Participants with acquired disabilities experienced more social isolation than those with congenital disabilities.

- **Stigma:** Notable disparities were seen in the sense of stigma ($p < 0.05$). Individuals with acquired disabilities experienced heightened societal stigma.

- **Life Satisfaction:** Notable variations were identified between the two groups on the life satisfaction measure ($p < 0.05$). Individuals with acquired impairments have lower life satisfaction levels compared to those with congenital disabilities.

A Pearson correlation analysis was performed to investigate the correlations among the variables. This analysis is essential in elucidating the correlation between the two variables and the nature of this correlation.

A negative link exists between self-esteem and social isolation ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that a decline in self-esteem correlates with an increase in the feeling of social isolation.

A negative link exists between stigma and life satisfaction ($r = -0.50$, $p < 0.01$). As the feeling of stigma escalates, life pleasure diminishes.

The findings of these statistical studies indicate that disability status significantly impacts the psychological well-being of people.

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

The sample size for this study was determined by the study's aims, research questions, and the statistical power of the analyses. The primary objective of the research was to assess the impact of acquired and congenital impairments on the psychosocial status of persons, necessitating a sufficiently large sample size to examine the attitudes of individuals with two distinct disabilities about psychosocial factors. Statistical power analysis was crucial in this approach, with a target power level of 80% or greater to enhance the likelihood of identifying a genuine impact in the studies. The sample size was chosen with enough power to guarantee the efficacy of statistical techniques, including t-tests and correlation analyses. Furthermore, the sample sizes of prior studies on analogous subjects were considered, and recognizing that sample sizes often range from 100 to 300 in the literature, the sample size for this research was established at 250 to ensure trustworthy and accurate findings. This size enhances the generalizability of the study's findings and bolsters the statistical significance of the results produced. The mean age of the participants is 35.6 years, with an age range spanning from 18 to 65 years. This age distribution encompasses a broad range of people, who constitute the target demographic of the research. The gender distribution is comprised of 52% female, 46% male, and 2% other. This allocation ensures equitable representation of both genders. The following figures illustrate the average age, gender distribution, work position, and marital status of the participants:

The participants had an average age of 35.6 years, with an age range from 18 to 65 years.

- 52% of participants are female, 46% are male, and 2% identify as other gender.
- Sixty percent of the individuals are working, whilst forty percent are jobless.
- 55% of participants are married, 40% are single, and 5% fall into other categories.

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When the disability status of the participants was examined, it was determined that 60% had acquired disabilities, 35% had congenital disabilities, and 5% had other disabilities. This distribution shows that the study was diversified to include individuals with different types of disabilities.

(The graphic is in Turkish, explanations are in the article.)

The graph above illustrates the distribution of participants in the research categorized by various forms of disability. The graph indicates that 40% of participants had physical disabilities, 20% had vision impairments, 15% suffered from hearing problems, 10% faced mental disabilities, and 15% had various forms of disabilities, including chronic illnesses, neurological, and

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psychiatric disorders. This distribution illustrates the variation among research participants regarding disability kinds and the representation of various impairments within the study.

Upon examining the geographical distribution of study participants by handicap type, significant disparities were identified. It was shown that the prevalence of physical disabilities was greater in major urban centers like Istanbul and Izmir relative to other areas; this phenomenon may be attributed to the impacts of heavy industry, traffic incidents, and occupational accidents in these metropolitan regions. Conversely, it was ascertained that the incidence of visual and auditory disabilities were more elevated in rural and underdeveloped areas. This scenario might be attributed to the challenges encountered in obtaining health care and the restricted options for early diagnosis in these areas. Furthermore, it was noted that the "other disability types" group, comprising 15%, including particular impairments such as chronic illnesses, neurological disorders, and mental issues, and exhibited regional variations. The data indicate that the geographical distribution of disabilities is contingent upon the accessibility of regional healthcare services and social support systems.

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Upon examining the educational qualifications of the participants, it is seen that 35% are university graduates, 25% are high school graduates, 20% possess a master's degree, 10% have a PhD, and 10% are graduates of basic or secondary education. This distribution indicates that the participants include diverse educational degrees. Regarding job status, 60% of the participants are employed, whilst 40% are unemployed. Regarding marital status, 55% of participants are married, 40% are single, and 5% fall into other categories. Regarding disability status, it was ascertained that 60% of participants had acquired impairments, 35% have congenital disabilities, and 5% fall into the other group. This distribution illustrates the variety of persons with disabilities who constitute the study's target population.

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The demographic attributes of the 250 participants in this research were assessed, and their distribution by city was evaluated. The bulk of participants originate from large cities, like Istanbul and Izmir. The distribution was conducted to guarantee representation of the target population, persons with disabilities, from various cities.

City Distribution: • Istanbul: 35% (n=88) of participants originate from Istanbul. Istanbul's status as Turkey's biggest metropolis, along with its substantial population, has contributed to this significant spread.

• Izmir: 25% (n=63) of participants originate from Izmir. Izmir is distinguished as a city where significant research is conducted on the inclusion of persons with impairments in societal activities.

• Ankara: 15% (n=38) of participants originated from Ankara. Given its status as the capital, there was considerable involvement from Ankara.

• Bursa: 10% (n=25) of participants originate from Bursa. Bursa's significance in industry and education has influenced this distribution.

• Other Cities: The remaining 15% (n=36) comprises participants from several large cities, including Antalya, Adana, and Konya. Participants from these cities enhanced the varied regional representation of the research. The predominance of major cities like Istanbul and Izmir enhances the study's sample structure, aligning with Turkey's demographic composition and the high population density in these urban areas.

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Self-Esteem Scale Results

The Self-Esteem Scale used in the research sought to assess the participants' self-esteem levels. Based on the scale findings, 65% of participants reported overall satisfaction with themselves, with an average score of 4.1 for this statement. The assertion of feeling worthless (reverse rated) yielded an average score of 2.2, accompanied by a 55% agreement rate. The expression of valuing individual accomplishments received a 72% favorable response, with an average score of 4.3. The assertion of self-sufficiency relative to others yielded an average score of 3.5, accompanied by a 48% agreement rate. Sixty percent of the participants reported seeing themselves positively, with an average rating of 3.9 for this statement. The agreement rate for the statement on occasional self-hatred (reverse scored) was established at 40%, with an average score of 2.8. Sixty-eight percent of participants with favorable self-perceptions affirmed this

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statement, resulting in an average score of 4.0. Upon analyzing the replies to the statement "believing that others possess greater talent," which was reverse scored, a 52% agreement rate and an average score of 3.1 were recorded. Ultimately, 70% of the participants reported seeing themselves as deserving of success, with an average score of 4.2 computed.

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Participation Rates for Self-Esteem Scale Statements

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The gender difference analysis in this research indicated considerable disparities in self-esteem levels across female, male, and non-binary individuals. Female participants reported more self-satisfaction, a heightened appreciation for their achievements, and a more favorable self-perception. Male participants often experienced feelings of worthlessness and sometimes self-hatred. Participants of other genders often assigned ratings around the mean values. The findings indicate that female participants typically exhibited elevated self-esteem, while male participants showed more internal criticism and negative self-assessment. Male participants often saw themselves as less capable as comparison to others; yet, their inclination to see themselves as deserving of success did not significantly vary from that of female and other gender participants. The results indicate that the sense of self-esteem among genders is

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influenced by social and cultural influences, which may impact women, men, and other genders differently. Generally, female individuals had superior scores in positive self-perception, while male participants seemed to prioritize internal assessment more significantly. This scenario offers significant insights on the manifestation of gender disparities in self-esteem and self-worth assessment.

Social Exclusion Scale Results

The Social Exclusion Scale was used to assess the degree of exclusion experienced by individuals in their social milieu. Seventy-five percent of participants reported feeling usually comfortable in the presence of their friends, with an average score of 4.2 for this statement. The agreement rate with the statement on feelings of exclusion when not invited to social activities was 55%, with an average score of 3.5. The agreement rate with the statement of experiencing loneliness in the social setting was 45%, with an average score of 3.1. Fifty-eight percent of participants reported feeling inadequately accepted in society, with an average score of 3.7 for this assertion. The mean score for the statement on reluctance to engage in social gatherings was 3.3, accompanied by a 50% concurrence rate.

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Participation Rates for Self-Esteem Scale Statements

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Stigma Scale Results

The Stigma Scale was used to evaluate the social stigma encountered by individuals as a result of their impairment. Sixty-five percent of participants said that others treated them differently due to their impairment, with an average score of 4.0 assigned to this statement. Sixty percent of participants said that disability hindered their complete acceptance by society, with an average score of 3.8 recorded. Forty percent of participants said that disability hindered their advancement at work, with an average score of 3.2 for this assertion.

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The Stigma Scale data indicate that 65% of participants reported experiencing differential treatment due to their handicap, with an average score of 4.0 for this assertion. Moreover, 60% said that their impairment hindered their complete acceptance in society, while 40% reported that it impeded their job advancement; the average scores for these assertions were calculated as 3.8 and 3.2, respectively.

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Life Satisfaction Scale Results

The Life Satisfaction Scale was used to assess the participants' overall life satisfaction. Seventy percent of the participants reported overall satisfaction with their life, with an average score of 4.1 for this statement. Sixty-five percent of participants said they had total control over their life, with an average score of 4.0 for this assertion.

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The examination of life satisfaction scores by gender included comparing the average scores assigned by each gender group to the life satisfaction scale. Seventy percent of female participants reported overall satisfaction with their life, with an average score of 4.1 for this assertion. Furthermore, 65% of women said they have total control over their life, with an

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average score of 4.0 for this assertion. The results indicate that female participants often exhibited elevated levels of life happiness, with social support and connections significantly contributing to this contentment. Sixty-five percent of male participants reported satisfaction with their life, yielding an average score of 4.0 for this assertion. Sixty percent of males reported feeling in control of their life, with an average score of 3.9 for this assertion.

For male participants, life happiness is more strongly associated with individual accomplishments and financial stability. Consequently, although men's life satisfaction ratings were somewhat inferior to those of women, they often demonstrated a substantial degree of contentment. In the opposite gender group, 60% reported overall life satisfaction, with an average score of 3.8 for this assertion. Fifty-five percent of this cohort believed they have total control over their life, with an average score of 3.7 for this assertion. The life happiness of people in the other gender group is intricately linked to societal acceptance and support for identity manifestations. The life satisfaction ratings of persons in this group are somewhat lower than those of other gender groups, however no significant difference exists. Women prioritize the gratification derived from social support and connections, while males place more significance on personal accomplishments and financial stability. Individuals in the alternative gender group demonstrate life pleasure derived from societal acceptance and support for identity expression.

Analysis of Open-Ended Questions

The responses to the open-ended questions elucidate the challenges encountered by participants about their disabilities and the impact of these circumstances on their lives. Forty-five percent of participants identified challenges in social interactions as the most significant effect of disability on their life, while thirty percent reported encountering barriers in work advancement. Of the challenges faced in social connections, 55% reported experiencing social isolation and stigmatization. Concerning the influence of handicap on professional life, 50% said that advancement chances in the workplace were restricted. Concerning the influence on self-

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esteem, 60% of the participants said that disability adversely affected them. Concerning the influence of impairment on overall life satisfaction, 55% of participants reported a detrimental effect on their life satisfaction.

These results provide a more thorough comprehension of the participants' experiences with impairment and the impact of these circumstances on their lives. The majority of individuals articulated challenges in social connections, indicating that social isolation and stigma are central to these issues. The challenges faced in work life underscore the influence of disability on career advancement. The stigma and social isolation linked to disability adversely impact the participants' psychological well-being and diminish their overall life satisfaction. The questions in the in-person interview format were deliberately organized to get a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences with disabilities. Questions on the initiation of the disability process seek to comprehend the participants' experiences and the impact of this process on their lives.

Inquiries on social exclusion and stigma seek to uncover participants' beliefs of their societal standing and the impact of these perceptions on their psychological well-being. Furthermore, inquiries on social support and life satisfaction seek to assess how participants appraise their existing support networks and the extent to which this assistance enhances their quality of life. Ultimately, inquiries on coping tactics and recommendations for enhancement sought to assess the efficacy of personal coping techniques and identify necessary adjustments in existing systems.

The results from the in-person interviews elucidated the significant impact of the participants' handicap experiences on their lives and their coping mechanisms throughout this process. The majority of interviewees highlighted that the onset of the impairment process marked a significant turning point in their life. This procedure often transpired abruptly and posed significant psychological challenges for the individuals. The participants said that the handicap precipitated significant alterations in their daily routines, prompting them to devise alternative coping techniques. Among these techniques, measures such as enhancing personal motivation, leveraging support networks, and using adaptive technology were particularly notable. The interviews examined how disability influenced the participants' self-perception and

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identity. Numerous participants said that the impairment first adversely affected their self-perception; but, with time, they underwent a process of acceptance and redefined their identities. The experiences of social isolation and stigma associated with disability have been a considerable cause of stress in the lives of participants. A multitude of participants reported feelings of exclusion or stigmatization in society due to their disabilities, which adversely impacted their psychological well-being. The prejudices experienced in their social milieu and the participants' responses to these biases led to challenges in their social connections.

The assessment of social support networks was very significant in the interviews. Participants said that the assistance they got from their families, friends, and communities significantly contributed to their capacity to cope with handicap. Participants who identified weaknesses in social support networks underscored the need for these services to be made more inclusive and accessible. The participants' life satisfaction was adversely impacted, particularly when community-based assistance was insufficient. Ultimately, participants conveyed their own ways for managing disability and offered recommendations for enhancing current support systems. Coping tactics including positive thinking, participation in activities like sports and the arts, and meditation. Participants underscored the need for enhancements in current health and social services, advocating for more accessibility and suitability to meet individual requirements. Participants often referenced the development of more effective support systems for addressing the issues associated with disability.

Discussion and Comments

The data acquired highlight the varying effects of disability kinds on people' quality of life, self-esteem, social exclusion, stigmatization, and life satisfaction. These results exhibit notable similarities and divergences when juxtaposed with the theoretical frameworks in the current literature.

Researchers in the literature, like Smart (2001) and Charmaz (1983), emphasize that congenital limitations often solidify people' identity perception and social acceptance processes. their is

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linked to the reality that persons with congenital impairments are identified by their identity throughout their lives and undergo social adaptation processes at an early age. Our research indicates that individuals with congenital impairments suffer social exclusion and stigmatization with less intensity, and their procedures of social acceptance are more straightforward.

Conversely, persons with acquired impairments have significant obstacles in relinquishing their former identities and adjusting to a new one. This discovery corroborates the observations of scholars such as Shontz (1975) and Goffman (1963) that acquired deficits result in more intricate psychosocial difficulties. A considerable number of participants highlighted the shock and mourning they encountered with the commencement of their impairment, observing that during this time, their self-esteem diminished and social isolation intensified. Our research also analyzed the geographical prevalence of disability kinds and determined that the occurrence of acquired impairments is elevated in major urban areas. This scenario has been associated with elements like industrial activity and vehicular accidents in these metropolitan regions. This conclusion corroborates Murphy's (1987) argument that social exclusion and stigmatization are more acutely experienced in metropolitan areas, hence complicating the social integration of persons with disabilities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research offers an in-depth examination of the psychological effects of congenital and acquired impairments on people. The results indicate that the nature of the handicap significantly influences several facets of an individual's existence, including quality of life, self-esteem, social engagement, stigmatization, and overall life satisfaction. Individuals with congenital impairments often undergo more consistent social acceptance processes and face reduced levels of social exclusion and stigmatization. Conversely, persons with acquired impairments, especially in the first phases of their disease, encounter more intricate psychological difficulties, such as shock, sadness, reduced self-esteem, and heightened social isolation.

The geographic distribution of disability categories underscores the influence of environmental variables, notably industrialization and urbanization, on the incidence of acquired impairments. In metropolitan areas, the prevalence of acquired disability is elevated, presumably because to causes such as industrial mishaps and vehicular accidents. The geographical disparities exacerbate the social integration of persons with disabilities, particularly in metropolitan environments where social exclusion and stigmatization are more prevalent. The results provide significant insights for formulating measures to enhance the quality of life for those with disabilities. An in-depth analysis of the mechanisms of social exclusion and stigmatization related to disability, together with initiatives to mitigate these phenomena, is essential for facilitating the social integration of persons with disabilities.

This study's results facilitate the formulation of strategic suggestions aimed at improving the quality of life and reinforcing the social integration of persons with disabilities. Initially, it is essential to develop tailored psychosocial support programs for persons with acquired impairments. These programs should concentrate on mitigating the difficulties faced, especially during the first phases of impairment, and should strive to enhance self-esteem, facilitate the bereavement process, and diminish social isolation. Such therapies may assist people in acclimating to their new identities and promote their enduring psychological well-being. Moreover, the execution of inclusive social policies that facilitate the integration of persons with disabilities into society is very significant. These policies must be formulated considering the diverse requirements of persons with congenital and acquired impairments, and should seek to tackle the particular issues they encounter. Such actions may enhance the involvement of persons with disabilities in societal activities while mitigating the dangers of stigmatization and social isolation.

Furthermore, it is essential to implement regional health and safety measures, specifically targeting the reduction of acquired disability rates in major urban areas. These endeavors must

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include the enhancement of occupational safety standards, the augmentation of traffic safety measures, and the elevation of public knowledge of the hazards linked to industrialization. These initiatives will aid in diminishing disability rates in major urban areas and guarantee that folks with disabilities may have safer lifestyles.

It is advisable to implement extensive public awareness programs to avert the stigmatization and social marginalization of persons with disabilities. These initiatives should seek to enhance public understanding of disability, underscore the significance of social acceptance, and render the contributions of impaired persons to society more prominent.

Limitations

This study's limitations relate to the generalizability of the results, the data gathering methodology, and the research scope. The sample's restriction to a particular geographic location may limit the generalizability of the results across other cultural and socioeconomic situations. The survey methodology is limited by social desirability bias and subjective replies. The research only examines certain psychosocial characteristics, excluding the influence of disability on other critical domains, like economic position and healthcare access. The cross-sectional methodology restricts the capacity to monitor the long-term impacts of impairment, underscoring the need for longitudinal investigations.

Notifications

Assessment: Conducted by both internal and external experts.

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Appendix 1

Survey Form: Comparative Analysis of the Psychosocial Effects of Acquired and Congenital Disabilities

Dear Participant,

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this survey. The survey aims to help us understand the psychosocial effects of acquired physical disabilities. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and your responses will be kept confidential. The survey will take approximately 15-25 minutes to complete.

Section 1: Demographic Information

Question No	Question	Options
1	What is your age?	☐ 18-25 ☐ 26-35 ☐ 36-45 ☐ 46-55 ☐ 56-65 ☐ 66 and above

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2	What is your gender?	☐ Male ☐ Female ☐ Non-binary ☐ Prefer not to say
3	What is your education level?	☐ Primary School ☐ Middle School ☐ High School ☐ Vocational School ☐ Undergraduate ☐ Master's ☐ Doctorate
4	What is your employment status?	☐ Full-time ☐ Part-time ☐ Unemployed ☐ Retired ☐ Student ☐ Other (Please specify): _____
5	What is your marital status?	☐ Single ☐ Married ☐ Divorced ☐ Widowed ☐ Other (Please specify): _____

Section 2: Disability Information

Question No	Question	Options
6	What type of disability do you have?	☐ Acquired Physical Disability ☐ Congenital Physical Disability ☐ Other (Please specify): _____
7	How long have you had your disability?	☐ Less than 1 year ☐ 1-5 years ☐ 6-10 years ☐ More than 10 years

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8	What is the cause of your disability?	☐ Accident ☐ Illness ☐ Congenital ☐ Other (Please specify): _____
9	What is the severity of your disability?	☐ Mild ☐ Moderate ☐ Severe ☐ Profound

Section 3: Psychosocial Scales

3.1. Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale):

Question No	Statement	Responses
10	Overall, I am satisfied with myself.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
11	Sometimes I feel like I am not good at all.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
12	I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
...	...	...

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3.2. Social Exclusion Scale:

Question No	Statement	Responses
13	I feel isolated from others.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
14	I feel that others do not want to interact with me because of my disability.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
15	I feel excluded when I am not invited to social events.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
...	...	...

3.3. Stigma Scale:

Question No	Statement	Responses
16	People look at me differently because of my disability.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree

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17	I feel that I am not fully accepted by society because of my disability.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
18	I experience discrimination because of my disability.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
...	...	...

3.4. Life Satisfaction Scale:

Question No	Statement	Responses
19	I feel that I have accomplished what I wanted in life.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
20	Overall, I am satisfied with my life.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
21	I think the conditions of my life are good overall.	☐ Strongly Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Neutral ☐ Agree ☐ Strongly Agree
...	...	...

Appendix 2

Interview and Open-Ended Questions Form

<i>Section</i>	Question Number	Questions	Explanations
<i>Section 1: Disability Experience</i>	1	How did your disability experience begin? How did you experience this situation? How has the onset of your disability affected your life?	Basic questions aimed at understanding the participant's disability experience and the onset of the condition.
	2	What are the biggest challenges you face due to your disability? What strategies do you use to cope with these challenges?	Aims to identify the daily life challenges associated with disability and the coping methods used to address them.
	3	How do you think your disability has shaped your identity and self-perception? How have you	Questions focused on understanding the impact of disability on the participant's identity perception and

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*Section 2: Social
Exclusion and
Stigmatization*

	dealt with or tried to deal with this situation?	psychosocial coping mechanisms.
4	Have there been times when you felt excluded from society because of your disability? How did you experience these situations and how did you respond to them?	Questions to understand the participant's experiences of social exclusion and their responses to these situations.
5	Have you ever felt stigmatized in your social environment because of your disability? How did these stigmatization experiences affect your psychological health and social relationships?	Aims to identify the psychosocial effects of stigmatization experiences and how these experiences impact social relationships.
6	How do you feel when you encounter prejudices related to your disability? How have you dealt with such situations?	Questions aimed at understanding the emotional responses and coping strategies of the participant when faced with prejudices.

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*Section 3: Social
Support and Life
Satisfaction*

7	How do you evaluate the social support you receive from your family, friends, or community? How has this support helped you cope with your disability?	Questions aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of social support systems and understanding the role these supports play in the participants' lives.	
8	Do you think the social support systems available to you are sufficient? What are the deficiencies or areas for improvement in these support systems?	Aims to identify perceived deficiencies in social support systems and areas where these systems can be improved.	
9	Are you generally satisfied with your life? How do you think your disability affects your life satisfaction?	Questions aimed at evaluating the participant's overall life satisfaction and understanding the impact of disability on this satisfaction.	
<i>Section 4: Coping Strategies and Improvement Suggestions</i>	10	What personal strategies do you use to cope with your disability? Do you think these strategies are effective?	Aims to identify individual coping strategies and evaluate the effectiveness of these strategies.

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11	What other strategies would you like to try to improve your psychosocial well-being? What changes would you like to see in the existing support systems?	Questions aimed at gathering participants' suggestions and identifying areas in the current support systems that need improvement.
12	To what extent have you benefited from healthcare services, social services, or community-based supports related to your disability? What are your suggestions for improving these services and supports?	Questions aimed at understanding the use of health and social services and evaluating the effectiveness of these services based on participants' experiences.
13	What changes should be made in society to improve the quality of life for individuals with acquired disabilities?	Questions aimed at identifying proposed societal changes and understanding how these changes could potentially impact the quality of life for individuals with disabilities.

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